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GC functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of vitamin D factor GC as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

Citations

1. Daiger, S.P., Schanfield, M.S. and Cavalli-Sforza, L.L., 1975. Group-specific component (Gc) proteins bind vitamin D and 25-hydroxyvitamin D. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 72(6), pp.2076-2080.